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Nutritional And Phytochemical Composition Of Tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*) From Different Cultivation Practices

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ABSTRACT

Tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) are widely consumed vegetables valued for their rich nutritional profile and diverse bioactive compounds. Variations in cultivation practices including conventional, organic, and integrated systems can significantly influence their nutritional quality and phytochemical composition. This study assessed the proximate composition (moisture, protein, fat, ash, fiber, and carbohydrates), selected micronutrients (vitamins and minerals), and key phytochemicals (lycopene, β -carotene, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds) in tomato fruits cultivated under different agronomic practices. Standard analytical methods were employed to determine nutrient and phytochemical levels, while statistical analyses evaluated differences among cultivation systems. Results indicated significant ($p < 0.05$) variation in nutrient and phytochemical concentrations, with organically cultivated tomatoes generally exhibiting higher levels of ascorbic acid, phenolics, and lycopene compared to conventionally grown counterparts. The findings underscore the role of cultivation practices in enhancing the nutritional and functional quality of tomatoes, with potential implications for consumer health and agricultural policy.

Keywords: Cultivation practices, Lycopene, Nutrients, Organic farming, Phytochemicals and *Solanum lycopersicum*,

INTRODUCTION

Tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) are among the most important horticultural crops worldwide, serving as a major dietary source of vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and phytochemicals (Raiola *et al.*, 2014). They are consumed both fresh and processed into various products, making their quality a key determinant of dietary nutrient intake. Beyond their culinary versatility, tomatoes have garnered considerable research interest due to their bioactive constituents particularly lycopene, β -carotene, flavonoids, and phenolic acids which have been linked to antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and disease preventive properties (Toor and Savage, 2006).

The nutritional and phytochemical composition of tomatoes is influenced by multiple factors, including genetic variety, environmental conditions, postharvest handling, and cultivation practices (Willer, *et al.*,

2020). Cultivation systems such as conventional farming (using synthetic fertilizers and pesticides), organic farming (emphasizing natural inputs and ecological balance), and integrated practices (combining aspects of both) can markedly affect soil health, nutrient availability, and plant metabolism, thereby altering fruit quality. Organic farming, for example, has been reported to enhance the accumulation of certain phytochemicals due to increased plant stress responses (ilahy, *et. al.*, 20011, Barrett, *et. al.*, 2007) while conventional systems may favor higher yield but potential dilute nutrient density.

Understanding how cultivation practices influence tomato quality is essential for guiding agricultural decision-making, improving nutritional outcomes, and meeting consumer demand for healthier foods. While previous studies have examined nutrient variations in tomatoes, there is limited comparative data on their phytochemical profiles under different cultivation regimes, especially in specific agro ecological contexts. This study therefore aims to evaluate and compare the nutritional and phytochemical composition of tomatoes grown under different cultivation practices, providing insights into the relationship between farming methods and fruit quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Sample Collection

Study was carried out in Kura Local Government of Kano State. Kura local government is located at Latitude 11.7723⁰ N and Longitude 8.42631⁰ E. Tomato samples were obtained from farms practicing three cultivation methods namely conventional, organic, and integrated systems, within the same agro ecological zone to minimize climatic variation effects. Fully ripe, undamaged fruits were randomly harvested from each farm, placed in sterile polyethylene bags, transported on ice to laboratory and analyzed within 24 hours.

Sample Preparation

Tomato samples from each cultivation system were washed with distilled water to remove surface contaminants, air-dried, and homogenized using a laboratory blender. The homogenized pulp was divided into portions for proximate, micronutrient, and phytochemical analyses.

Proximate Analysis

Moisture, ash, crude protein, crude fat, and crude fiber contents were determined using standard AOAC (2019) methods. Carbohydrate content was calculated by difference.

Micronutrient Analysis

Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content was determined by 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol titration. Mineral elements (Ca, Fe, K, Zn) were quantified using atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS) after wet digestion of samples.

Phytochemical analysis

Lycopene and β -carotene were determined spectrophotometrically after extraction with hexane-acetone-ethanol mixture, following Rodriguez-Amaya and Kimura (2004) method. Total phenolic content was measured using the Folin Ciocalteu method, while total flavonoids were estimated using aluminum chloride colorimetric method.

Statistical Analysis

All analyses were conducted in triplicate. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Differences among cultivation systems were evaluated using one-way ANOVA, and were separated using Turkey's HSD test at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS.

Nutritional and phytochemical composition of Tomatoes from different cultivation practices (mean \pm SD)

Parameters	Conventional
Moisture (%)	93.20 \pm 0.40
Protein (%)	1.15 \pm 0.05
Fat (%)	0.25 \pm 0.02
Ash (%)	0.58 \pm 0.03
Fiber (%)	0.90 \pm 0.04
Carbohydrate (%)	4.92 \pm 0.18
Vitamin C (mg/100g)	16.20 \pm 0.60
Lycopene (mg/100g)	8.25 \pm 0.28
β -Carotene (mg/100g)	3.15 \pm 0.12
Total phenolic (mg/100g)	55.20 \pm 1.80
Total flavonoids (mg/100g)	18.60 \pm 0.65

Values with $p < 0.05$ indicate significant differences among methods.

DISCUSSIONS

The results of this study demonstrated that cultivation practices significantly influence the nutritional and phytochemical composition of tomatoes. Organic tomatoes exhibited notably higher protein, ash, fiber, vitamin C, lycopene, β -carotene, total phenolics, and flavonoids compared to conventional and integrated systems. These findings are consistent with earlier reports by Hallmann (2012), Worthington (2001) and Caris –veyrat *et. al.*, (2004), who attributed the enhanced nutrient density in organically grown produce to slower growth rates, increased soil organic matter, and absence of synthetic inputs that can alter plant metabolic pathways.

The higher vitamin C content observed in organic tomatoes may be linked to increased oxidative stress in plants grown without synthetic pesticides, which stimulates antioxidant biosynthesis as part of the plant's defense mechanism (Mitchell *et al.*, 2007). Similarly, the elevated levels of lycopene and β -carotene suggest that organic cultivation promotes carotenoid accumulation, possibly due to improved soil micronutrient availability and greater sunlight exposure in less densely planted organic fields.

The total phenolic and flavonoid contents were also significantly higher in organic tomatoes, supporting the hypothesis that plants under mild biotic and abiotic stress synthesize more secondary metabolites as protective agents (Bourn & Prescott, 2002). Phenolic compounds are known for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, which can contribute to reducing the risk of chronic diseases.

Although conventional farming systems produced tomatoes with slightly higher moisture content, there was no significant difference in carbohydrate content across the three cultivation systems. This suggests that the primary effect of cultivation practice lies in micronutrient and phytochemical profiles rather than macronutrient carbohydrates.

Integrated farming systems generally yielded intermediate values between organic and conventional systems, indicating a potential compromise between yield optimization and nutritional enhancement. These results highlight the importance of cultivation methods in influencing not only yield but also the nutritional and functional quality of tomatoes.

CONCLUSION

This study confirms that cultivation practices significantly affect the nutritional and phytochemical profiles of tomatoes. Organic cultivation produced tomatoes richer in vitamin C, lycopene, β -carotene, phenolics, and flavonoids compared to conventional and integrated systems, suggesting potential health benefits for consumers. The findings reinforce the role of sustainable agricultural practices in enhancing the nutritional quality of food crops. Adopting cultivation practices that promote nutrient and phytochemical accumulation can contribute to improved dietary quality and public health outcomes. Future research should investigate the influence of soil management, varietal selection, and postharvest

handling on nutrient retention, as well as conduct sensory and consumer preference studies to complement the biochemical data.

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